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Synthesis and Pharmacological Screening of Bio-Active Molecule Fluoro-Benzothiazole Comprising Sulfonamido Quinazoline Derivatives

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ABSTRACT

Various..substituted..6[6-fluoro-7-chloro-(1,3)benzothiozoyl-2-aminosulphonyl] (5z)-5[4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-4-imidazolonyl]-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline and 6[6-fluoro-7-chloro-(1,3)benzothiozoyl-2-aminosulphonyl](5z)-5[2-hydroxybenzylidene-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-4-imidazolonyl]-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline...Containing different functional groups have been synthesized by treating substituted 2-amino benzothiazoles with 3-carboxy-4-N-acetylamino benzene sulphonyl chloride in presence of ethanol and pyridine, further it is treated with hydrazine hydrate then followed by oxazolone in presence of pyridine. The identity of compounds were confirmed on the basis of their spectral (UV-Visible, IR, ¹H NMR, and Mass) data. Further they have been screened for their antimicrobial, anthelmintic and anti-inflammatory (*in-vitro*) activities.

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Introduction:

Fluorobenzothiazole¹⁻⁴ comprising sulfonamide quinazoline derivatives have been synthesized and evaluated for their various activities. The sulfonamide⁵⁻¹⁴ drugs were the first effective chemotherapeutic agents to be employed systemically for the prevention and cure of bacterial infection in human beings. The introduction of trimethoprim and sulphamethoxazole has resulted in increased use of sulfonamide for the treatment of specific microbial infection. Benzothiazoles with sulphonyl group and quinazoline etc were reported to possess various pharmacological activity of clinical importance. The chemistry and pharmacology of quinazoline¹⁵⁻¹⁹ have been of great interest because quinazoline derivatives possess various biological activities. This includes antimicrobial, anticonvulsant, antineoplastic, analgesic and antiinflammatory etc. Therefore in present work we have prepared sulphonamido-quinazoline incorporate with substituted benzothiazole.

Materials and methods:

Melting point was determined by open capillary tube method and are uncorrected. T.L.C was run on silica gel G plates using butanol, ethyl acetate and Benzene (1:2:1) as developing solvent for the purity of the compounds. I.R. Spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR Spectrophotometer by using KBr pellet technique.

Experimental:

Synthesis of 3-amino-N-(7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline-6-sulphonamide : A mixture of 2(acetylamino)-5-[(7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)sulphamoyl]benzoic acid (4.48g, 0.01 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.5ml, 0.01mol) in ethanol was refluxed on a water bath for 3 hrs. The content was cooled and poured on crushed ice, filtered and washed with water. The isolated product was crystallized from ethanol.

A mixture of 3-amino-N-(7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline-6-sulphonamide (4.44g, 0.01mol), 2-phenyl-4-p-dimethyl aminobenzylidene-5-oxazolone (2.59g, 0.01mol) in pyridine (10ml) was refluxed in an oil bath for 6 hrs at 120^o. The contents were cooled and poured on crushed ice, filtered and washed with water. The isolated product was crystallized from ethanol.

Results and Discussion:**1) Anti-bacterial activity²⁰⁻²⁵**

Synthesis and pharmacological screening of 6[6-fluoro-7-chloro-(1,3) benzothiazol-2-aminosulphonyl](5z)-5[4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-4-imidazolonyl]-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline and 6[6-fluoro-7-chloro-(1,3)benzothiazol-2-aminosulphonyl](5z)-5[2-

SCHEME-I

R= o,m,p, nitro,

R' = morpholine

o,m,p, chloro,

piperazine

H

o,m,p, methoxy

SCHEME-II

R= o,m,p, nitro

o,m,p, chloro

H

o,m,p, methoxy

P-carboxy phenyl

R'= morpholine

piperazine

hydroxy benzylidene-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-4-imidazolonyl]-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline were tested for the antibacterial activity against following bacteria's like ;

- i] *Staphylococcus aureus*, ii] *Streptococcus fecalis* (gram +ve) and
iii] *Escherichia coli*, iv] *Klebsilla pneumoniae* (gram -ve).

The test compounds S₃, S₈, S₉, V₅, V₆, and V₁₂ showed moderate antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve) at lower and higher concentration compared to standard drug procaine peniciline.

The compounds S₉, S₁₁, S₁₂, V₁, V₄, and V₁₁, showed promising antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* (gram-ve) at both concentration as compared to standard drug streptomycine. The test compounds S₂, S₆, and V₇ showed moderate antibacterial activity against *Streptococcus fecalis* (gram +ve) at lower and higher concentration compared to standard drug procaine peniciline. Compounds S₁₂, V₇, V₁₁, showed promising antibacterial activity against, *Streptococcus fecalis* at higher concentration as compared to standard drug procaine penicillin. Compounds S₄, S₅, S₈, S₁₁, S₁₃, V₄, V₆, V₈, and V₁₁, showed promising antibacterial activity against, *klebsiella pneumoniae* (gram-ve) at lower and higher concentration.

2) Anti-fungal activity :

Were tested for antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*.

Among the compounds tested; S₁₀, V₁ and V₁₀, showed significant activity against *Candida albicans* at lower concentration compared to standard Ciclopirox olamine USP.

Among the compounds tested; V₄, V₈ showed comparatively better antifungal activity against *candida albicans* at both concentrations compared to Ciclopirox olamine USP.

V₁, V₂, V₃, V₁₀ showed significant activity against *Aspergillus fumigatus* compared to standard Ciclopirox olamine USP.

3) Anthelmintic Activity²⁶⁻²⁸:

Among the compounds tested S₁, S₃, S₄, S₆, and V₃, V₆, V₇, showed significant paralytic time of earthworms compared to standard drug Albendazole, at all 0.1, 0.2, 0.5% concentrations of compounds.

4) Anti-inflammatory activity²⁹⁻³⁰ (Invitro) :

Were tested for anti-inflammatory activity by using inhibition of albumin denaturation technique compared to standard Ibuprofen. Among the compounds tested S₄, S₁₃, V₇, V₁₀, showed moderate anti-inflammatory activity compare to standard Ibuprofen (74.15%).

Summary and Conclusion:

In present work, fluorochloroaniline was treated with KSCN in presence of bromine in glacial acetic acid and ammonia to get 2-amino-6-fluoro-7-chloro (1,3)-benzothiazole, which is then refluxed with 3-carboxy-4-N-acetylaminobenzene sulphonylchloride in presence of ethanol for 4 hrs in oil bath to get 2(acetylamino)-5-[(7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,3-benzothiazol-2yl)sulphamoyl] benzoic acid, which upon treatment with (0.01 mol) hydrazine hydrate and refluxed for 3 hrs in water bath by using ethanol as a solvent to get 3-amino-N-(7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,3-benzothiazol-2yl)-2-methyl-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazoline-6-sulphonamide. The above product is then refluxed with (5z)-5-[4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene]-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (P-dimethylamino benzaldehyde) **or** (5z)-5-(2-hydroxy benzylidene)-2-phenyl-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one (salicylaldehyde) in oil bath for 6 hrs by using pyridine as a solvent. The above said mixture was refluxed with different aromatic amines, PABA, morpholine and piperazine in presence of DMF to get newly targeted compound through replacing chlorine at 7th position.

The synthesized compounds were characterised by Solubility, TLC, Analytical data, UV-visible, IR, ¹HNMR and Mass spectral studies.

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